

Digital Trust in Insurance: Toward a Conceptual Framework

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Abstract. As digital transformation accelerates, digital trust has become a strategic imperative, particularly in the insurance industry, where stakeholder confidence and the handling of sensitive data are central. Despite growing academic attention, the concept of digital trust remains fragmented and lacks clear definitions and industry-specific frameworks. This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, integrating a systematic literature analysis across relevant disciplines, a qualitative case study with semi-structured interviews, and a design science research approach. The findings indicate that digital trust is a multidimensional construct requiring the integration of technical, organizational, and ethical considerations into business operations. Based on these insights, this study develops and empirically validates a management-oriented Digital Trust for Insurance (DT4I) framework to support trust management in the insurance sector.

Keywords: Digital Trust, Insurance, Cybersecurity, Digital Trust Framework.

1 Introduction

Digital transformation is fundamentally changing how the insurance industry operates [1]. Increasingly, interactions between insurers and customers are mediated through digital channels—such as mobile apps, online portals, and artificial intelligence (AI)-driven systems—rather than through personal contact [2]. While this shift promises efficiency and scalability, it also presents new challenges: loss of human interaction, data security concerns, and a lack of transparency in automated processes [3]. These developments have given rise to the concept of digital trust, which refers to the confidence stakeholders have in the reliability, integrity, security, and ethical behavior of digital systems and platforms [4]. According to Asprion et al. [1] for insurers, digital trust is crucial—not only to protect sensitive data, but also to build long-term relationships in an environment where face-to-face interaction is increasingly replaced through digital-supported interactions. The insurance sector is particularly affected due to highly sensitive data, long-term policyholder relationships, and complex regulatory requirements [5]. As noted by Kluiters et al. [6], digital trust is becoming a strategic differentiator in financial services and insurances, particularly as customers grow more aware of data usage and digital risk. However, current approaches tend to address digital trust only partially—often limited to compliance or cybersecurity—without considering broader dimensions such as ethical data governance, algorithmic fairness, or corporate digital

responsibility [7, 8]. This study aims to close this gap by exploring the following research questions:

1. How is digital trust defined and understood in the insurance sector?
2. What dimensions are relevant from a stakeholder perspective?
3. How can trust principles be integrated into governance and digital strategies?

Despite a growing body of literature on digital trust, most existing research focuses on technical aspects, such as cybersecurity, authentication, and platform design [1, 3, 9]. While these aspects are important, prior research largely overlooks the organizational, ethical, and sector-specific dimensions that are particularly relevant for trust in the insurance industry. While prior frameworks encompass key organizational dimensions, including governance, risk management and compliance (GRC), corporate digital responsibility (CDR), and stakeholder-oriented expectations, they largely omit an explicit treatment of digital trust as a coherent and integrative construct [10, 11]. This is particularly problematic in insurance, where long-term relationships, sensitive data, and complex regulatory obligations intersect.

Existing digital trust related models—such as those from ISACA [12] or the World Economic Forum [7]—provide valuable foundations but lack practical transferability to insurer workflows and decision contexts. The lack of an actionable, management-oriented framework tailored to the insurance industry constitutes the core research gap addressed by this study.

This study contributes by (a) synthesizing a conceptual understanding of digital trust based on academic and industry-specific literature, (b) contextualizing digital trust within the insurance industry by identifying sector-specific needs and vulnerabilities, (c) providing empirical insights from insurance practitioners that validate theoretical constructs and highlight practical challenges, and (d) laying the foundation for a digital trust framework for the insurance industry, abbreviated as **DT4I** framework to be further developed and validated in future research.

1.1 Origins and Conceptualization of Digital Trust

The concept of trust has been extensively studied across psychology, sociology, and organizational science: early foundational work by Deutsch [13] defined trust as a behavior involving risk-taking based on the expectation of positive outcomes. Rotter [14] emphasized the reliability of another's word or promise, while Zand [15] introduced the notion that trust inherently involves vulnerability to potential loss. By the 1980s, trust was being analyzed as a multi-dimensional construct, combining cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components [16]. Later, Moorman et al. [17] linked trust to confidence in trading partners, particularly in uncertain or fragile environments, while McKnight et al. [18] introduced trustworthy beliefs and intentions as distinct constructs.

According to Mayer et al. [19] trust is framed as *“the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the actions of another party based on the expectation that the other will perform a particular action important to the trustor, irrespective of the ability to monitor or control that other party”* (p. 712). This widely accepted formulation integrates psychological, relational, and behavioral elements of trust.

Trust has also been explored through a leadership lens, emphasizing how feelings of competence, consistency, and fairness foster trusting relationships within organizations [20–22].

Emergence of Digital Trust. As digital technologies began mediating more social and business interactions, a new form of trust was required – digital trust. In contrast to traditional trust, which often depends on personal interaction and physical presence, digital trust is rooted in confidence in technological systems and institutional behaviors [8, 9, 23]. Digital trust emerged from the need to facilitate interactions in environments where users cannot directly verify the trustworthiness of their counterparts. Instead, users rely on platform security, data privacy policies, and the perceived integrity of systems [3, 4]. For example, platforms based on distributed ledger technologies like blockchain can establish trust not through relationships but through technical guarantees of immutability and decentralization – rendering traditional mechanisms like relational bonding obsolete [24, 25].

Definitions of Digital Trust. Several definitions of digital trust have been proposed over the past two decades. Bailey et al. [26] stress the role of platform design in influencing user perceptions of trustworthiness. Corritore et al. [9] define digital trust as “*an attitude of confident expectation in an online situation of risk that one’s vulnerabilities will not be exploited.*” Akram and Ko [27] focus on historical behavioral consistency as the basis for trust. Mattila and Seppälä [23] point to technical foundations: security, identifiability, and traceability. Pietrzak and Takala [8] emphasize organizational responsibility in maintaining credibility, security, and reliability. Dobrygowski [7] introduces a societal and ethical lens, suggesting digital trust includes the expectation that technology protects stakeholder values. Launer et al. [3] define it as the alignment of technology, people, and processes with digital expectations. Numan and Sunna [12] describe digital trust as “*the confidence in the integrity of the relationships and transactions among providers and consumers within a digital ecosystem*”. The distinctions between traditional and trust and digital trust are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Distinctions between traditional trust and digital trust.

Aspect	Traditional Trust	Digital Trust
Basis	Personal relationships	Systems and technology
Interaction	Face-to-face, synchronous	Online, asynchronous
Validation	Intuition, history	Encryption, policies, certifications
Dominant risk factor	Human behavior	Cyber threats, data misuse
Regulatory environment	Social norms, contracts	GDPR, FADP, ISO standards

1.2 Multidimensional Nature of Digital Trust

Digital trust is a complex and multidimensional concept that encompasses a range of interrelated dimensions [5, 7], each of which plays a critical role in fostering, strengthening, and sustaining confidence in digital interactions as well as in the management and protection of data; these key dimensions are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Dimensions of Digital Trust.

Dimension	Description	Sources
Security	Security is fundamental to digital trust, protecting data and interactions from unauthorized access and cyber threats through encryption, authentication, and system monitoring. Security ensures that stakeholders can trust the integrity and confidentiality of their data.	[23]
Privacy	Privacy ensures personal data is handled responsibly and in compliance with regulations, supported by transparent practices and user consent. Organizations must implement policies and practices that respect and protect stakeholder privacy, thereby fostering trust.	[4]
Reliability	Reliability denotes the consistent performance and availability of digital systems, fostering stakeholder confidence. Stakeholders must be able to trust that digital platforms will function as expected.	[12]
Transparency	Transparency involves clear communication about data usage, security protocols, and incidents, enabling informed decision-making. Transparency helps build trust by providing stakeholders with the information they need to make informed decisions.	[3]
Accountability	Accountability requires organizations to take responsibility for digital operations, demonstrated through audits, standards adherence, and continuous improvement.	[8]
Compliance	Compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks reinforces trust and mitigates risk. Therefore, not only prevents legal penalties but also enhances stakeholder trust by demonstrating a commitment to high standards.	[12]
User Experience	A well-designed user experience (UX) enhances trust through intuitive, secure, and responsive interfaces.	[28]
Ethical Practices	Ethical practices uphold fairness, autonomy, and societal values in digital interactions, and therefore align organizational actions with stakeholder values.	[8]
Historical Consistency	Historical consistency strengthens trust by demonstrating a sustained commitment to high standards over time. Consistent performance and reliability reinforce trust, strengthen stakeholders' confidence.	[27]

1.3 Stakeholders of Digital Trust

Digital trust emerges through the interactions of multiple stakeholders whose interests often intersect. Identifying these stakeholders is therefore crucial, as their differing expectations and vulnerabilities must be recognized and addressed in a holistic manner. These dimensions are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Stakeholders of Digital Trust from an Organization’s Perspective.

Stakeholders	Description	References
Users	Customers, clients, and the public who engage with an organization’s digital resources, expecting secure and trustworthy interactions, and rely on the organization to safeguard their personal information.	[3, 8]
Customers	Transactional stakeholders who demand protection of financial and personal data, with digital trust being key to loyalty.	[8, 12]
Employees	Employees relying on secure systems to perform effectively, with digital trust supporting data protection, morale, and productivity.	[3, 4]
Authorities & Regulators	Authorities and regulators require compliance with legal standards, and digital trust reflects adherence to data protection and cybersecurity regulations.	[7]
Partners & Suppliers	Depending on secure and reliable digital collaboration with trust facilitating operational efficiency.	[8, 12]
Investors & Shareholders	Relying on digital trust to assess organizational stability and growth. Trustworthy digital practices can enhance investor confidence, leading to increased investment and support, impacting the organization's reputation, financial performance and increasing firm value.	[6–8]
The General Public	Non-customers, shaping an organization’s reputation through perceptions of digital trustworthiness.	[6, 7]
External Auditors & Security Experts	Assessing and verifying the integrity and security of an organization’s digital systems. Their trust in the organization’s digital practices is essential for validating compliance and identifying vulnerabilities.	[29]

1.4 The Role of Digital Trust in Insurance

Unlike most industries, insurers make promises about future performance—pay claims, protect data, and support policyholders in times of need. This time-delayed value proposition makes trust a prerequisite for customer engagement and retention [8, 30]. In the digital age, the basis of trust is shifting from interpersonal relationships to digital systems [7]. Digital trust in insurance is not only a risk mitigation strategy but a strategic enabler for innovation and transformation. As insurers adopt technologies like AI, blockchain, and telematics, they must ensure that customers, partners, and regulators perceive these systems as trustworthy. Insurers that actively build digital trust can: (a) increase digital adoption [4], (b) strengthen customer loyalty [4], (c) differentiate from competitors [12], and (d) accelerate innovation [31,32]. In addition, the insurance sector faces several critical digital trust-related risk areas. Data sensitivity and privacy are key concerns, as insurers process highly sensitive information such as health records, financial data, where breaches can cause significant legal and reputational damage [33].

The increasing use of algorithmic decision-making in underwriting and claims processing raises concerns regarding transparency, fairness, and potential bias [4, 9]. Furthermore, insurers are frequent targets of cybersecurity threats, including ransomware and phishing attacks [34]. Finally, strict regulatory requirements such as the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR) require continuous compliance to maintain stakeholder trust [33].

2 Research Strategy

Design Science Research (DSR) based on Hevner et al. [36] was selected as the research strategy. By adopting DSR, a systematic research process for the development and evaluation of an applicable artifact was ensured to enhance digital trust in insurance, ensuring both academic rigor and practical relevance. Literature [36, 37] outlines the iterative nature and process orientation of design science, in which artifacts are continuously refined through cycles of design, rigor, and relevance. DSR can be structured in five main phases: (1) awareness of problem, (2) suggestion, (3) development, (4) evaluation, and (5) conclusion [37]. This process-oriented approach was chosen for the development of DT4I.

2.1 Awareness and Suggestion Phase

The awareness phase focused on identifying challenges and opportunities related to achieving digital trust, specifically within the insurance industry. Building on the theoretical background (section 1) the suggestion phase aimed to develop potential solutions for the research gap identified. Key elements and dimensions of digital trust were derived from established frameworks, theoretical models, and documented issues, ensuring both relevance and conceptual rigor. This phase also produced an initial conceptualization of the DT4I framework integrating theoretical foundations while addressing sector-specific gaps. Furthermore, preliminary hypotheses regarding DT4I's requirements were formulated, providing the basis for subsequent validation.

2.2 Development Phase

This phase was built on a three steps approach: (1) existing digital trust frameworks were analysed to identify a suitable conceptual foundation, (2) as result that one recognised framework [5] was selected as guiding framework and compared with digital trust dimensions and key elements derived from the literature, (3) a new insurance specific framework—the DT4I framework—was developed by integrating these insights. Based on the identified conceptual gaps from literature analysis, the first version of the DT4I framework was developed by extending the structure of ISACA's DTEF [5] with an additional conceptual element referred to as the **assurance node**. This node integrates four domains that collectively support the establishment and maintenance of digital trust within insurances and represent key organizational capabilities required to foster digital trust in complex digital ecosystems.

2.3 Evaluation phase

This phase focused on systematically assessing the DT4I framework's modifications and their alignment with the research objectives. The evaluation process was conducted in two stages to ensure feedback on the framework's clarity, scope, relevance, and completeness. In the first stage, the DT4I was presented and validated through a qualitative workshop involving C-level executives from a leading insurance company, including the chief technology officer (CTO), chief risk officer (CRO), chief information security officer (CISO), and other senior leaders. This process aimed to gather detailed qualitative feedback, identifying strengths and areas for improvement to refine the DT4I for the subsequent validation round. In the second validation round, a three-point Likert scale was used to assess the clarity of the DT4I framework's modifications. This efficient method suited participants already familiar with the DT4I framework from the earlier workshop. Its purpose was to confirm broad agreement or highlight major areas of improvement. The participants were the focus group members, selected for their prior involvement and detailed understanding of the DT4I framework.

2.4 Conclusion phase

The final phase focused on synthesizing and concluding the research. Its purpose was to integrate insights from all preceding phases to evaluate the overall success of the study and outline directions for future work. This stage also included a methodological reflection on the applied research strategy. This phase assessed whether the artifact met the research objectives rigorously and yielded practical contributions. It summarized the framework's alignment with identified challenges, its operationalization, and its practical relevance. The phase further examined the artifact's theoretical contributions, particularly its value for understanding digital trust in the insurance sector and its ability to unify previously fragmented concepts. Finally, this phase reflected on the DSR approach, reviewing the iterative process, stakeholder engagement, and validation methods. This ensured transparency and rigor while providing guidance for future methodological improvements.

3 Results

The developed DT4I framework provides a management-oriented structure for addressing digital trust challenges in the insurance industry. The framework acts as an umbrella model that supports decision-makers in managing digital trust across organizational, technological, ethical and regulatory contexts with focus on the insurance sector. Overall, digital trust is not static but evolves with changes in stakeholder expectations, technological innovation, and regulatory environments. The DT4I framework therefore provides a structured approach for aligning organizational practices with stakeholder expectations and industry-specific trust requirements according to the expectations of ISACA's DTEF [5].

The resulting DT4I framework extends ISACA's DTEF [5] by introducing an additional assurance node that addresses sector-specific trust and audit requirements in insurance organizations. The DT4I framework consists of five nodes: (1) People, (2) Organization, (3) Process, (4) Technology, and (5) new—Assurance. The original nodes and domains of ISACA's DTEF remain unchanged and can be directly applied within the extended framework structure of the DT4I framework (see Fig. 1). This adaptation ensures that the conceptual elements of ISACA's recognized DTEF [5] can continue to be used; it is expected that this will increase acceptance of new DT4I framework.

Figure 1. Digital Trust for Insurance Framework (DT4I)

The primary contribution of the DT4I framework lies in the introduction of the assurance node, which integrates four domains that collectively support the development and maintenance of digital trust: (1) Transparency, (2) Responsibility, (3) Integrity, and (4) Resilience—see the arrows starting from the assurance node (Fig. 1). These domains reflect key organizational capabilities required to manage trust within digital ecosystems and were derived through a structured gap analysis comparing existing digital trust frameworks with sector-specific requirements and feedback from the interview partners during the DT4I framework evaluation phase (section 2.3).

3.1 Transparency

The Transparency domain focuses on ensuring that stakeholders clearly understand how digital interactions and data processing activities are managed within the organization. It emphasizes open and accountable communication regarding organizational processes while maintaining the security and integrity of data. Transparency supports trust by enabling stakeholders—including customers, regulators, and partners—to evaluate how digital services operate and how data is handled. In the insurance sector, transparency is particularly important due to the sensitivity of customer data and the need to ensure fairness and accountability in claims management and underwriting processes.

3.2 Responsibility

The Responsibility domain ensures that organizations act in a fair, ethical, and accountable manner toward all stakeholders. It emphasizes responsible digital practices that extend beyond regulatory compliance and reflect a commitment to ethical standards and corporate responsibility. Given the sensitive financial and personal data managed by insurers, this domain highlights the importance of proactive governance and responsible decision-making in digital environments. The domain also connects organizational culture and stakeholder relationships by emphasizing responsible interactions within the broader digital ecosystem.

3.3 Integrity

The Integrity domain focuses on maintaining ethical conduct and compliance with regulatory requirements across both internal operations and external partnerships. In the insurance industry, integrity is a critical component of trust, particularly in relation to secure data handling and reliable service delivery. By emphasizing ethical principles and adherence to regulatory standards, this domain supports the development of trustworthy relationships with customers, regulators, and other ecosystem partners. It also ensures that organizations maintain high standards of accountability across their digital operations.

3.4 Resilience

The Resilience domain addresses the organization's ability to maintain operational continuity in the face of disruptions. It emphasizes the protection of data integrity, confidentiality, and system availability while ensuring that organizations can recover quickly from operational incidents or cyber threats. In the insurance sector, resilience plays a critical role in maintaining stakeholder trust during crises. The domain therefore highlights the importance of cybersecurity, business continuity management, and adaptive organizational capabilities that enable insurers to sustain critical services within digital ecosystems.

4 Discussion and Future Research

The newly developed and validated DT4I framework extends existing digital trust models by integrating governance, cybersecurity, and ethical considerations into a sector-specific management framework. By introducing the assurance node and its four domains, the framework addresses key trust-related challenges in the insurance industry while maintaining compatibility with ISACA's DTEF [5]. The findings reveal the proposed management-oriented DT4I framework effectively addresses the critical challenges identified in the study. The DT4I developed synthesizes fragmented concepts, addresses industry-specific challenges, and serves as a tool for fostering trust in an increasingly digitalized environment.

Existing digital trust research is fragmented and often lacks a comprehensive, integrated perspective. By incorporating key elements of GRC, CDR, and cybersecurity, this study offers a management-oriented framework that advances the conceptual understanding of digital trust in the insurance sector. Illustrating how the assurance node and its domains serve to unify these domains into a single cohesive model. Compared with broader and holistic frameworks for all industries, such as ISACA's DTEF [5], the developed DT4I framework is uniquely tailored to address the specific requirements of the insurance sector and bridges some identified non-insurance specific gaps as well. The new framework focuses on fostering trust through operational continuity, ethical governance, and robust data protection, addressing sectoral nuances that are often overlooked in generalized models.

DT4I provides insurance companies with a structured approach to understanding and managing digital trust challenges. Despite being in its foundational stages, the framework has the potential to (a) facilitate strategic discussions on digital trust, (b) guide the alignment of organizational practices with stakeholder expectations, and (c) support regulatory compliance and enhance operational resilience. By focusing on actionable domains, the framework offers a pathway for operationalization within insurance organizations. For instance, the transparency domain emphasizes clear communication with stakeholders, whereas the Integrity domain ensures adherence to both ethical principles and regulatory standards. These elements collectively enhance the organization's ability to foster trust in its digital interactions. Nonetheless, practitioners would benefit from further refinement of the DT4I framework to include detailed guidance on operationalization. Drawing from ISACA's DTEF [5] approach, the addition of specific Practices, Activities, KPIs, and KRIs would enhance the DT4I framework's usability, enabling organizations to measure performance, track progress, and identify areas for improvement. These refinements are essential for bridging the gap between theoretical understanding and practical implementation in the insurance industry.

This study establishes an initial foundation for digital trust in the insurance industry, but further work is required to refine and extend the DT4I framework. While the DT4I framework covers key domains such as transparency, responsibility, integrity, and resilience, it remains conceptual. Future research should develop concrete activities and measurable indicators to support practical implementation and enable organizations to assess maturity and progress. Although designed for insurance, the framework may be relevant to other trust-dependent sectors such as healthcare or finance.

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